

Pot screening for drought tolerance in rice

P. Gomathinayagam, Upland Genetic Evaluation and Utilization (GEU) Training; and K. T. Ingram and M. A. Maguling, Agronomy Department, IRRI

Screening rices for drought tolerance in the field requires extensive facilities. We tested a method for screening rices grown in pots, using minimal facilities. The method corresponds to the protocol followed at IRRI for drought screening in the field and for drought tolerance under limited rooting depth.

Three replications of 18 rice genotypes were dibble seeded in 5-liter pots containing Maahas clay soil in the IRRI greenhouse in Sep 1987 (see figure). Pots were irrigated daily to keep the soil saturated to 30 d after seeding (DAS). Then irrigation was stopped and water deficit was allowed to develop to 40 DAS, when plants of susceptible check IR20 were apparently dead. Then all pots were re-irrigated. Recovery from stress was evaluated at 45 DAS.

Varieties differed significantly in maximum root length at 45 DAS, root dry weight, shoot length, leaf dry weight, leaf area, leaf water potential,

Pot screening for drought tolerance at 5 d after stress onset. IRRI, 1988.

and SES scores (see table). Salumpikit (resistant check) and IR47686-1-4B showed the greatest drought tolerance, IR20 and ARC7098 the least.

All growth, physiological, and *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) parameters except shoot length were significantly ($P < 0.05$) correlated

with one another. The most efficient parameter for dividing genotypes into the greatest number of classes was leaf water potential.

Average SES scores of susceptible and resistant checks from this pot screening were significantly correlated with average scores from field drought tolerance trial results in the IRRI data bank ($r = 0.95$, $P < 0.01$).

The best parameters to study growth or physiological characteristics are root and shoot dry weights. Measuring root and shoot dry weights requires only drying and weighing facilities. Leaf water potential and leaf area, although strongly related to drought resistance, require moderately expensive apparatus.

Root length did not discriminate genotypes well at 45 DAS and shoot height did not correlate with any other parameters.

The disadvantages of pot screening over field screening are that fewer genotypes may be studied, and only the early vegetative growth may be assessed. The advantages are that growth and physiological parameters are easily studied; trials may be conducted during any season with minimal greenhouse or other rain shelter; and pot screening is relatively inexpensive. □

Selected growth parameters measured at 40 DAS and SES drought resistance scores at 2, 5, and 10 bars soil moisture tension (10-cm soil depth) and recovery after reirrigation of 18 genotypes in a greenhouse pot trial. IRRI, 1987 wet season.

Genotype	Root length (cm)	Root dry wt (g)	Shoot length (cm)	Shoot dry wt (g)	Leaf area (cm ²)	Leaf water potential (bar)	Drought resistance score ^a			
							2 bar	5 bar	10 bar	Recovery
IR47686-1-4B	20	0.14	45	0.52	39	-13	0	1.0	3.0	1.0
Salumpikit (tolerant check)	19	0.13	53	0.47	38	-13	0	1.0	3.7	1.0
IRAT288	17	0.08	50	0.21	30	-16	1	5.0	5.0	3.7
ISDA10	17	0.07	49	0.24	32	-20	1	5.0	5.0	4.3
CNA4130	17	0.06	46	0.23	30	-17	1	5.0	5.0	5.7
IRAT115	17	0.08	45	0.28	29	-18	1	5.7	5.7	4.3
CNA4120	16	0.10	52	0.35	18	-17	1	5.7	6.3	5.7
CNA4164	16	0.08	49	0.30	34	-26	1	5.0	6.3	5.7
CNA4196	17	0.09	50	0.32	36	-25	1	5.0	6.3	5.7
AUS196	16	0.07	50	0.26	18	-26	3	7.0	7.0	3.7
CNA4143	17	0.08	51	0.31	30	-15	1	5.7	7.0	4.3
AUS257	17	0.11	50	0.38	22	-21	3	7.0	7.0	5.0
IAC165	17	0.07	52	0.26	23	-20	1	5.0	7.0	6.3
CNA4102	15	0.09	47	0.35	28	-21	1	5.0	7.0	7.0
HD14	12	0.06	51	0.21	28	-28	3	6.7	8.3	7.7
AUS454	12	0.06	51	0.20	20	-20	4.3	7.0	8.3	7.7
ARC7098	11	0.03	48	0.11	14	-31	3	7.0	9.0	9.0
IR20 (susceptible check)	12	0.02	42	0.09	21	-32	3	7.0	9.0	9.0
Mean	16	0.08	49	0.29	27	-21.0	1.6	5.3	6.4	5.4
LSD (0.05)	2	0.01	4	0.09	12	1	1.2	1.2	2.9	2.6

^aSES scale: 0 = no symptom, 9 = dead.